

THE USAGE OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. This article indicates natural-cultural and universal characteristics of proverbs in English and Uzbek proverbs. Also, it explains and compares some proverbs which are used in famous writers' works.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi maqollarning tabiiy-madaniy hamda umumiy xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, mashhur yozuvchilarning asarlarida qo'llanilgan maqollar tahlil qilib taqqoslanganligi ketilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье приводятся природно-культурные и универсальные характеристики пословиц в английских и узбекских пословицах. Также в нее вошли некоторые пословицы, которые используются в произведениях известных писателей.

Key words: language, folklore, sayings, comparative, express, character.

A proverb is a brief saying that presents a truth or useful wisdom. It is usually based on common sense or practical experience. The effect of proverb is to express wisdom as self-evident. The same proverb often occurs among several different people. True proverbs are sayings that have been passed from generation to generation primarily by word of mouth, or may have been put in written form. The book of proverbs in the Old Testaments of the Bible includes notable collection of such sayings as: "Hope deferred makes the heartsick", "A good name is rather to be chosen than great riches. The Book of proverbs according to (Benjamin 1958) is very useful to ancient Israelites who were educated primarily at home. The values of these proverbs reflect the teaching of parents trying to raise their children to become successful and responsible adults. Every language has its own stock of proverbs, and proverbs in one language today reflect every age and time. It contains keen observation of everyday life, constitute popular philosophy of life, and provide an insight into human behavior and character.

There are several types of proverbs describe below: Universal proverbs – On comparing proverbs of culturally unrelated parts of the world, one finds several ones having not only the same basic idea but the form of expression, i.e. the wording is also identical or very similar. These are mainly simple expressions of simple observations or simple ethical concepts, but not all

expressions of simple observations became proverbs in every language. Regional proverbs – In culturally related regions - on the pattern of loanwords - many loan-proverbs appear beside the indigenous ones.

A considerable part of them can be traced back to the classical literature of the region's past, in Europe the Greco-Roman classics, and in the Far East to the Sanskrit and Korean classics. Local Proverbs – In a cultural region often internal differences appear, the classics (e.g. the Bible or the Confucian Analects) are not equally regarded as a source of proverbs in every language. Geographical vicinity gives also rise to another set of common local proverbs. These considerations are illustrated in several European and Far-Eastern languages, as English and Korean. Proverbs were always the most vivacious and at the same time the most stable part of the national languages, suitable competing with the sayings and aphorisms of outstanding thinkers. In the proverbs and sayings picturesqueness of national thinking was more vivid expressed as well as their features of national' character. The proverbs and sayings are the paper of folklore which is short but deep in the meaning.

They express the outlook of the amount of people by their social and ideal functions. Proverbs and sayings include themselves some certain features of historical development and the culture of people. The semantic sphere of proverbs is very wide and cannot limit them. The proverbs describe every branch of people's life. The fact is that proverbs and sayings are similar in meaning in spite of their diversity in form and language.

M.Zhumabayev the Kazakh famous poet and writer said: “It is not necessary to educate children the same as who educates them but they must be educated to the future requirements... Every tutors teaching methods are moral values of Kazakh nation”.

There are various sources about the history of proverbs. In order to become a proverb, a statement must be perceived and assimilated by ordinary people. The turning of a word phrase into a proverb becomes part of public consciousness, who invented the proverb does not matter. We can safely assume that any proverb was created by a certain person in certain circumstances, but for many old sayings, the source of their origin is completely lost. Consequently, giving opinion about the original proverbs that were created from the collective wisdom of the people is much more correct. In the set of propositions, summarizing the daily experience, the meaning of words, apparently, grew into the shape of proverbs gradually, without any explicit declaration.

Figurative reflection of reality in the proverb associated with the ethical evaluation of various phenomena of life. That is why some proverbs express funny, and sad, and funny and even bitter things, senility and youth.

Here we will be giving some proverbs expressing senility as well as youth and their translation. Wild oats, To sow one's - Yoshlik — beboshlik - Молодо — зелено, погулять велено. Youth and age will never agree - (Yoshlik va qarilik hechqachon kelisholmas.) - Yosh ketaman deb qo'rqitar, Qari — o'laman deb - Вчеммолод похвалится, втомстарпокается. Youth will serve - (Yosh — xizmatda.) - Yoshkelsa — ishga, Qarikelsa — oshga- Молодой на службу, старый на совет.

The contrastive analysis undertaken in this study began with form. The formations of the English proverbs collected in the data are in terms of SVOCA.

In Uzbek proverbial formation was in some cases in form of VP+VP, VP+ Adj. Phr, while in most cases conforms to the regular pattern of SVOCA (NP+ VP +NP). The notions of form in English proverbs are words that signal conventional pattern (i.e. regular word arrangement to form meaning). For example:

Birds are not to be caught with chaff

Care killed a cat

Cock crows, As the old/ so doth the young -

In Uzbek, it is also words that signal conventional pattern but in some cases different pattern that is distinct from English such as:

Qari qushni tuzoq bilan tutib [aldab] bo'lmas

Qayg'u qaritar, g'am o'ldirar

Yosh xo'roz qari xo'roz singari qichqiradi.

The analyses of proverbs showed that, the structure of English and Uzbek proverbs mainly partially corresponds: Measure **thrice** before you cut **once** - **Yetti** o'lchab **bir** kes; A man can only die **once** — **Bir** boshga **bir** o'lim; Every bean has its black — Har zog'da **bir** dog'; The moon is not seen when the sun shines - **Yetmish** yulduz yarim oyga tanimas;

Complete correspondence of proverbs with numeral component is rarely observed:

Two heads are better than **one** — **Bir** boshdan **ikki** bosh yaxshi; There are **two** sides to every question- Har yaxshida **bir** ammo bor, Har yomonda **bir** lekin; **Two** of a trade never agree — **Ikki** qo'chqor kallasi **bir** qozonda qaynamas; Have more brains in one's little finger than **one** has in his whole body-**Yuzta** axmoqdan **bitta** aqli zo'r; **Two** blacks

do not make a white — **Ikki** yomon qo`shilsa keng dunyoga sig`ishmas; Hear **twice** before you speak **once** — **Ikki** marta tinglab, **bir** marta gapir; The voice of one man is the voice of no **one-Bir** daraxtdan bog` bulmas yoki yolg`iz otning changi chiqmas; **One** fool makes many-Ahmoq elchi **ikki** tarafni buzadi and others.

In most cases the structure of English and Uzbek proverbs containing numerals do not correspond, i.e. absence of correspondence is often observed: As a hen with **one** chick — Hovliqqanga sichqon teshigi **ming** tanga; There is not an ounce of love in a thousand pounds of law — Qozilashgan qarindosh bo`lmas; All covel, all lose-**Ikki** kemaning boshini ushlagan g`arq bo`ladi; An ass between **two** bundles of hay — **Ikki** quyonning ketidan quvgan **ikkalasidan** ham quruq qoladi; To make to bites of a cherry-Mayizni **qirq** bo`lib yesa **qirq** kishiga yetadi and etc.

Conclusion

This article tried to explain the meaning of proverbs in both languages. Proverbs are not only observed in works or stories, but also people use certain proverbs to express their thoughts and for increasing speech effectiveness. Summing up, we can say that both English and Uzbek languages are rich in proverbs, the Uzbek proverbs contain more numerals than English ones.

The list of used literature:

1. Hrisztova-Gotthardt, H. (Ed.) & Aleksa Varga, M. (Ed.) (2015). Introduction to Paremiology. A Comprehensive Guide to Proverb Studies. Berlin: De Gruyter Open.
2. J. Raymond. 1956. Tensions in Proverbs: More Light on International Understanding. Western Folklore 15.3, pg 134-139.
3. "T-shirt with anti-proverb". Neatoshop.com. Retrieved 2013-08-30.
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Proverb>

